

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: GANA

FIRST NAME: AHMED

PROGRAM CODE: PHGH

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software (MS Word Professional plus 2013)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Process and Structure of Academic Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021,7-12)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
3. United Kingdom versus United States English (EUCLID 2021, 24-31)
4. Rules of Thumb in Academic Writing (EUCLID 2021, 12-14)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Enrolling in Euclid University to pursue a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Global Health and Health Systems is a “dream come true.” I have nurtured this idea for a long time but could not achieve it due to work pressure and other exigencies. The EUCLID long-distance program will allow me to realize this dream while doing routine office work. I have reviewed the ACA-401D (period 1) course and its content and found it helpful and exciting. It provides the foundation for academic writing, appropriate English language use, and the importance of consistency using the United Kingdom (UK) or United States (USA) versions but not both on the same document. The Chicago/*Turabian* citation style is the gold standard for EUCLID for in-text and footnote references. However, other referencing styles are also acceptable. Plagiarism is an academic offense and must be minimized to an acceptable level. My impression of the teaching approach at EUCLID using course materials, audio-visuals, and contact with instructors and supervisors is positive, as it will ensure effective and quality learning outcomes.

In this response paper, I will discuss the process and structure of academic writing, how to avoid or minimize plagiarism, style guides, American versus United Kingdom English, and rules of thumb in academic writing.

2) PROCESS AND STRUCTURE OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

I understand academic writing as an art that has to be learned and mastered by anyone interested in writing academic materials. It requires a certain minimum standard of quality to be accepted for publication. The academic writing process is flexible, but specific basic steps are needed to accomplish the process (EUCLID 2021, 7.) These include starting the process early to give the writer sufficient time to read about the topic under review, plan well, and implement. The writer must define the question that his research work seeks to address and write down his plan for the work. Planning for an academic essay allows the writer to document his thoughts and ideas about the topic, lay out steps for executing the work, and provide answers to the question being addressed.

A good essay requires the writer to review relevant literature on the topic and document what he knows and needs to know about the topic. Notes should be taken while researching the topic, and all quoted work should be cited appropriately. “Creativity and critical thinking are sine quo none in essay writing, enabling the writer to expand his ideas and narrow the focus or scope of his work” (EUCLID 2021, 9-10). Once the required information is obtained, the actual writing of the draft essay can commence using a standard framework. The essay consists of at least three major parts, including an introduction, the body of the essay, and a conclusion. The Introduction is aimed at describing the topic from a general to specific perspective, responding to the question briefly by putting it in the form of a thesis, and laying out the process and plan for the intended work. The essay’s body systematically answers the question, discussing issues rationally with evidence and references for work cited. The conclusion provides a synopsis of the significant issues described in the essay and answers the essay’s question powerfully, from specific to general.

Once the essay has been drafted, the writer reviews the document after a couple of days, checks his references, makes necessary edits, and re-drafting before sharing it with a colleague to read further. He then submits to the intended destination based on the approved guidelines. This descriptive process of writing academic essays is very systematic and comprehensive, and I find it convenient and straightforward to read and use.

3) PLAGIARISM

I understand plagiarism as using or copying other people’s work without acknowledging the original authors. Using another author’s work without the required citation and reference is an academic offense. “Credit must be given to the original authors of any work used when using any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data or visual” (EUCLID 2021, 34). While a certain percentage of plagiarism is allowed and acceptable (up to 25%) for a good reason and accompanied by citation, plagiarism (as low as 14%) is considered an academic offense without appropriate citation and referencing (EUCLID 2022, 1). However, plagiarism must be made minimal to be acceptable. Writers should, as much as

possible, change the wordings used by the original authors by paraphrasing them using their own words and understanding without changing the meaning described by the original author.

Plagiarism comes in two forms, and both are unacceptable. The first one is when the author's words are used without quotation marks, even when footnotes are added. Similarly, incomplete paraphrasing also falls under this type of plagiarism. The second is when ideas are taken from a source without footnoting the source (EUCLID 2021, 14.)

4) USE OF UNITED STATES VERSUS UNITED KINGDOM ENGLISH

While it is acceptable by the Euclid University rules to use both versions of English mentioned above. It is academically unacceptable to use both in the same paper. Adopting either of them and remaining consistent throughout the document ensures the quality of the essay written. Some words' spellings may differ, and their pronunciation may be the same (for example, axe and ax, plough and plow, colour and color). In others, spellings may remain the same, but their pronunciation differs, for example, advertisement (advert, ad). I found this explanation very useful because I had previously used both on the same document while writing essays. There are also instances where the term is the same, but spelling and pronunciation are different (for example, Aluminium-aluminum, Maths - math). In other instances, words may be the same but with different or additional meanings (EUCLID 2021, 26).

The adopted English variant used is usually set up at the beginning of the writing using the review/language section of the computer; this helps a lot in auto-correcting spellings and their appropriate use.

5) RULES OF THUMB IN ACADEMIC WRITING

The rule of thumb is an essential guide when writing an academic paper. Given below are some key points to remember and use when writing: staying focused, writing clearly, supporting assertions made, avoiding tedious and clumsy writing, discussing views intensely, avoiding plagiarism, and avoiding conclusions using sweeping generalities. Sentences should not exceed five lines maximum, while paragraphs should remain 20 lines and below. Stylistic variety adds color to the writing, thus making it more attractive to the reader (EUCLID 2021, 13).

6) STYLE GUIDES

“Style guide is a means of documenting a writer’s approach to certain key elements of writing style that need to be consistent” (EUCLID 2021, 41). These guides ensure that standards are applied and maintained across several writings from different authors, thus ensuring that publications are consistent and coherent. Style guides also ensure consistency in the length of sentences, use of abbreviation, use of active or passive voice, structure, use of symbols, terminology used, spelling using UK or US English, manuscript layout, accepted language, and many other essential aspects of writing (EUCLID 2021, 41). There are several types of style guides available for different professional writing groups. The Chicago/Turabian style is the goal standard for EUCLID, but other styles may also be used depending on the course the writer pursues. The World Health Organization (WHO) style and the American Psychology Association (APA), Harvard, and Oxford are examples.

7) CONCLUSION

Academic writing is a technical process with norms, values, and standards, which every writer must learn and use consistently. A written essay has essential parts that introduce the question being addressed by the research work, a body that discusses the issue more extensively, and a closing part that summarizes the key points described in the essay. Appropriate use of a variant of the English language and correct use of punctuations and styles are essential in ensuring the quality of the paper and avoiding plagiarism by using quotation marks and paraphrasing.

REFERENCES

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